

VISARPA VYADHI AND IT'S AYURVED MANAGEMENT- A CASE STUDY

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Article Received on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 05 Jan. 2026,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18152545>

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How to cite this Article: *1Dr. Sushma Shete, 2Dr. Rupali Patil (2026). VISARPA VYADHI AND IT'S AYURVED MANAGEMENT- A CASE STUDY. "World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(1), 1373-1384. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Visarpa is very common disease mentioned in *Ayurveda* text. According to *Acharya Charak* *Visarpa* is *Raktvaha Strotodushtijanya Vyadhi*^[1] which spreads in the body in various directions and manifests as *Daha, jwar, Pitikotpatti, Aaraktvarnata, Shopha* and *Shula*. According to modern concept Herpes zoster is a viral infection caused by reactivation of the Varicella zoster virus which remains dormant in a nerve root ganglia of the cranial nerve or the dorsal root ganglia after a previous Varicella infection. Reactivation maybe apparently spontaneous (as usually occurs in middle aged or elderly) or be due to immunosuppression (as impressions with malignant disease or AIDS).^[2] A 45year female complaining with vesicular lesions on left side of abdominal region associated with the *Daha, Shula, Aaraktvarnata, Kandu* on local lesions. *Raktmokshan* with *Siravedha* was done immediately by letting

out 50 ml of blood from left cubital fossa. She was administered with 250mg of *Kamdhudha Ras (Sadha)* twice a day before meal with *Sheetjal, Chandrakala Ras* 250mg twice a day after meal with *Sheetjal, Paripathadi Kwath* 20 ml twice a day with *Sambhag Sheetjal, Nishottar Churna* 3gm with *Godugdha* at night after meal and *Shatdhuat Ghrita* mixed with *Suvarn Gairik* for local applications on the lesions. The patient reported significant relief in *Daha* on first day after *Raktmokshan* and on 5th day there was diminish size and shape of lesions and other symptoms. The scars limited to minimal without any inflammatory signs on

7th day of follow up. Given medicines are easily available and cost effective *Ayurvedic* formulations which can be used in management of *Visarpa*.

INTRODUCTION

According to *Ayurvedic* classics *Twacha Rogas* are produced due to imbalance of *Tridoshas* which causes *Dhatudushti* mainly *Raktdhatu Dushti*. As per conventional medical field skin is an organ which is supplied by blood vessels and it is rich in hair follicle and sweat glands. Any abnormal changes in this components causes skin disease. Skin diseases are diseases which affect emotional, psychological and social well-being. Thus skin diseases has a negative impact on person's life. The incidence of Herpes zoster ranges from 1.2 to 3.4 for 1000 person per year among younger healthy individuals while incidence is 3.92 to 11.8 per 1000 person per year among patients older than 65. According to the study conducted in India higher incidence of Herpes observed in younger age group (21 to 40 years of age). Recent studies available that the incidence of skin problem and skin diseases caused by virus are increasing. Herpes zoster is a painful disease which is characterised by localised painful spread of skin rash and blisters. The first symptom is usually severe and continuous pain in the distribution of the affected nerve route. After 3 to 4 days the skin in the affected area becomes reddened and vesicles appear which dry up over 5 to 6 days leaving small scars. The pain of the zoster subside as eruption fades but may be follow by neuralgia.^[3] *Ayurved* classics mention that *Visarpa* spreads like a snake and thus it is considered as *Pradhan Vyadhi*. It is an *Ashukari Vyadhi* (acute disease) of skin. Many patients continue to suffer from moderate to severe pain known as post herpetic neuralgia which affect till many years

CASE REPORT

A 45 year female patient came to OPD with Chief complaints: Acute skin eruptions preceding severe pain and burning sensation on left side of abdominal region since two days.

History of past illness- patient is known case of hypertension since one year, taking regular antihypertensive medications.

Surgical history- History of hysterectomy done 3 years back No history of any addiction

Ahara: Vegetarian diet, 3 times /day, *Sarvarasatmya*, *Katu Raspreeti*, *Viruddhanna Sevan*, *Paryushitanna Sevan*

Vihara: Exposure to *Aatap* and *Vayu*

Nidra: *Prakruta* before the onset of symptoms and disturbed since few days

Ashtavidha Pareeksha: Analysis

Naadi: Pittakaphaja, Mandukahamsagati

Mala: 1 time /day, Prakruta

Mutra: Pita varna, Sadahamutrata, Mutralpata since 1 week

Jivha: Alipta, Rukshata

Shabda: Deenavaak

Sparsha: Ushnasparsha

Druk: Diminished vision, Uses spectacles

Aakruti: Madhyamakaya

Dashavidhapareeksha: Analysis

Prakruti: Pittakapha

Vikruti: Pitta pradhana tridosha vikruti

Satwa: Pravara

Saara: Pravara

Samhanana: Madhyama

Ahara Shakti:

Abhyavaharana Shakti: Madhyama;

Jarana Shakti: Madhyama

Vyayama Shakti: Madhyama

Satmya: Madhyama

Pramana: Madhyama kaya, Weight: 70kg, Height: 158cm, BMI: 28

Vaya: Madhyama

Vikrutipariksha: Samptapti Ghataka

Dosha: Pitta pradhana Tridosha

Dushya: Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Ambu

Agni: Mandagni

Agni dushti: Rasadhatwagnimandhya

Srotas: Rasavaha, Raktavaha, Mamsavaha, Ambuvaha

Srotodushti: Sanga

Udbhavasthana: Adho-amashaya

Vyakthasthana: Vamparshwa, Vamabhaga of Udarpradesh

Sancharasthana: Sarvasharira

Rogamarga: Aabhyantara

Rogaswabhava: Aashukari

Sadhya-asadyata: Yaapya

General Examination

Pallor: Absent

Icterus: Absent

Cyanosis: Absent

Clubbing: Absent

Lymphoedenopathy: Left axillary lymph nodes – tender to touch and mildly swollen

Oedema: Absent

Vital Examination

Vitals

Pulse rate: 78/min Heart rate: 78/min

Blood pressure: 140/90 mm of Hg Temperature: 98.6 F

Systemic Examination

Respiratory System: Normal breath sounds heard, no added sounds. Cardiovascular system: S1S2 heard – No added sounds

Central Nervous System: intact, concious, oriented Per Abdomen: Soft, Non-tender.

Signs and Symptom

Daha (Burning Sensation)

Shoola (Pain) *Kandu* (Itching) *Pidikas* (Vesicle)

Rakatavarniya pidika Antardaha

Local Examination

On Inspection:

Distribution of the lesion: There was a small area of erythema on the left lateral and left side of abdominal region which extended towards right side of it with a few tiny blisters. Lesions found consisting of grouped, tense, Superficially seated vesicles distributed unilaterally along a dermatome on the left lateral, left side of abdominal area and left side of back. Otherwise there was no herpetic rash over the rest of her body.

On palpation: The area was tender to touch and there is rise of temperature locally

Rakta (Blood), *Lasika* (Lymph), *Mansa* (Flesh) and three *Doshas* (*Vata*, *Pittaj* and *Kapha*) and 7 elements are involved in pathogenesis of *Visarpa*.⁽⁹⁾

Etiology of *Visarpa*

The *Nidan* of *Visarpa* can be included under different headings like a *Aahar*, *Vihara*, *Panchakarma* procedure and as an *Updrava* of other *Vyadhi*.

The following are causative factors of *Visarpa*^[10]

Excessive indulgence in *Lavan* (salt), *Amla* (sour), *Katu* (pungent) and *Ushna* (hot ingredients) as well as in *Amla Dadhi* (sour curd), *Dadhi Mastu* (whey), *Shukta* (Vinegars), *Sura* (type of liquor), *Sauviraka* (type of wine), *Vyapanna Madya* (contaminated wine), excessive liquor or heat induced *Raga* (condiments) and *Sadhava* (confectionery), use of *Vidahi* (causing burning) *Dravya*. *Kilat* (cheese), *Harita* (Lashunadi *Harita* group), *Mandaka* (immature curd), *Kurchika* (inspissated milk), use of *Sandaki* (fermented wine), *Paishtika* (One made up of *Pistmai Padarth* or pastries), *Til Tail* (sesame oil), black gram and horse gram, use of flesh of domesticated wetland and aquatic animals and garlic, use of *Praklinna* (putrified food), *Asatmya* (Unwholesome) and *Viruddha* (mutually contradictory ingredients) *Aahar*. *Atyashana* (over eating), *Deevaswapa* (sleeping during daytime), *Ajirnashan* (eating during indigestion), *Adhyashana* (eating food immediately after the meal), *Kshatat* (traumatic injury), *kshat* (wounds), *Bandha* (ligatures), *Prapatan* (trauma due to falls), *Atap Sevan* (over exposure to Sun), strainful work, poisons, poisonous air, burns etc.

Due to *Hetusevan* the provoked *Vatadi Doshas* affect *Rakta*, *Lasika*, *Twak* and *Mansa* and spreads in the body.

Bahirashrit Visarpa i.e. Externally situated (pathogenesis in *Shakha*, *Ras Dhatu* and *Rakta Dhatu*, *Antarashrit Visarpa* i. e. internally situated (pathogenesis in internal organ and other *Dhatus*) and *Ubhayashrit* i. e. situated in both (externally as well as internally) pathways to be known more and more serious consecutively.

Externally situated with *Sadhya* (curable), internally situated *Visarpa* is *Kashtasadhya* (very serious and difficult to cure) where as externally as well as internally situated type is *Asadhya* (incurable).

***Samprapti* of *Visarpa*^[11]**

Due to *Hetusevan* there is vitiation of *Tridosh*. These vitiated *Doshas* causes *Agnimandya* which leads to *Aamotpatti*. The *Ama* results in vitiation of *Mansa*, *Rakta* and *Twak*. *Visarpa* is caused by *Dosha Dushya Sammurchhana* in *Abhyantar* or *Bahya* path which causes development of *Vistrut*, *Anunnat Shopha* that has *Sarpana Pravrutti* associated with *Daha* and *Shula*.

According to modern medicine Herpes is caused by *Vericella zoster* virus which affects the central nervous system internal organ and muscular is surfaces predominantly. Herpes zoster is a viral infection which causes painful rashes or blisters on the skin. The *Varicella zoster* virus is spread through direct skin to skin contact with the fluid that oozes from the blisters. After receiving treatment for primary infection sometimes the virus goes into the dormant stage in the ganglion. Due to some triggering agents such a trauma, ultraviolet light, change in cell mediated immunity the virus get reactivated again.^[12]

Lakshana of Visarpa^[13]

Vataj Visarp is the result of obstruction caused by aggravated *Dosha*. Show the resemblance to the skin infection such as *Erysipelas*. Its clinical features are burning sensation, fever, pain, affected area becomes edematous and red, small blackish or reddish blisters with thin clear reddish and scanty discharge are seen. In *Pitta* dominant *Visarpa*, *Pitta* aggravated by the use of hot regimen, by eating irritant and sour foods vitiates the susceptible body elements and by feeling the vessels, begins to spread. Pustules are Formed in the affected part causing intense pain and Burning sensation. It can be co-related with the skin diseases such as *Erysipelas*, *Herpes* and *burns* etc. *Kaphaja Visarpa* spreads slowly in the body and it Shows resemblance to the *Erysipelas*. It causes fever, Vomiting, chills etc. The affected area becomes edematous, red with pale colored eruptions covered by thick skin. In *Agni Visarpa Vata-Pitta* vitiated severely due to their respective etiological factors and strengthened mutually, spreads producing severe burning pain in the body. The patient affected with this type of *Visarpa* feels as if his body is sprinkled with flaming coals. One suffering from *Agni-Visarpa* is to be regarded as incurable. In *Kardam Visarpa* excessively aggravated *Kapha Pitta* due to their respective etiological factors, spreads in the body causing suppuration of the tissues in particular part. It is localized and spreads with slow speed. The affected Part becomes muddy, black, dirty, unctuous, excess hot, heavy, dull aching, edematous, with deep seated suppuration, having no discharge, rapidly become sloughy, sweated, suppurated, having putrid flesh and skin, gradual little pain, when touched bursts and gives space on

pressing, throws out decomposed and putrefied flesh, shows blood vessels, ligaments and has cadaverous smell and causes disturbed consciousness as well as memory. This is called *Kardam Visarpa* and is incurable. In *Granthi Visarpa*, Kapha and Vata gets vitiated due to the use of firm, heavy, hard, sweet, cold, unctuous, and *Abhishyandi* (which increase discharges and cause obstruction) ingredients of diet, lack of physical exercise etc., not following preventive seasonal *Panchakarma* purification. The *Visarpa* which is caused by all etiological factors, manifesting with all signs and symptoms, spreads in all body elements very rapidly and great disastrous is known as *Sannipataj Visarpa*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Visarpa Chikitsa

Shodhan Chikitsa

According to *Acharya Charak Raktmokshan* is *Ardhachikitsa* in the treatment of *Visarpa*.^[14] *Raktmokshan* was done by *Siravedha* method. Written consent is taken from patient. Call procedure is described to patient. *Siravedha* is done with number 18 through left brachial fossa. *Siravedha* was done as per sop, 50 ml blood was let out.

Shaman Aushadhi Chikitsa

Drug	Dose	Duration	Anupan
Kamdudha Ras	250 mg BD	Before meal	Sheet jal
Chandrakala Ras	250 mg BD	After meal	Sheet jal
Paripathadi Kwath	15 ml BD	After meal	Sheet jal
Nishottar Churna	3 gm HS	After meal	Godugdha
Shatdhaut Ghruta	LA BD		

OBSERVATION AND RESULT

Raktmokshan

Raktmokshan (*Siravedha*) was done immediately from left brachial fossa. *Shyav*, *Aruna*, thick blood let out.

Shaman Aushdhi

Reduction in *Pitika* over abdominal surface was noted. Relief from *kandu* Relief from *Daha* *Shaman Aushadhi* continue for 21 days.

Day	<i>Daha</i>	<i>Kandu</i>	<i>Shula</i>	<i>Pitika</i>
1	++	++	+++	++++
7	+	+	+	+
14	-	-	-	+

21	-	-	-	-
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DISCUSSION

Kamdudha Ras^[15]

Kamdudha Ras is one of the best *Kalpa* which is used in management of *Pitta Pradhan Vyadhi*. *Shankh Bhasma*, *Shautik Suvarna Gairik*, *Guduchi Satwa* are ingredients in it. *Kamdudha* has immuno modulator, antioxidant and anti-virus effects and can be used internally in management of *Visarpa*

Chandrakala Ras:^[16]

Chandrakala Ras contains *kajjali*, *Tamra Bhasma*, *Abhrak Bhasma* with *Bhavna* of *Musta*, *Dadim*, *Durvamul Swaras*, *Ketki*, *Sahdevi*, *Kumari*, *Parpata*, *Usheer*, *Madhumalati*, *Shatavari* and mixed with *Kutki*, *Guduchi Satwa*, *Parpatak*, *Usheer*. Then all these ingredients are processed by 7 *Bhavna* of *Mrudvika Kwath*.

It acts on *Pittajanya Vyadhi* and reduces the *Daha* in *Visarpa*.

Paripathadi Kwath:^[17]

Paripathadi Kwath is explained in *Panchbhautik chikitsa* of Vd. Datar Shastri. This *Kalpa* contains *Dravya* which are *Kashaya* and *Tikta Ras Pradhan*. So it reduces *Kshariya Guna* of *Rakta Dhatu*.

Suvarna Gairik Churna and Goghrut Lepa

Suvarna Gairik Churna^[18] and *Goghrut* both have *Pittaghna* and *Daashaman* property. *Lepa* of these locally reduces *Daha* and Redness quickly.^[19]

Trivrutta Churna^[20]

Trivrutta has *Katu*, *Tikta*, *Kashaya*, *Madhura Ras*, *Katu Vipaka* and *Sheet Veerya*. It is *Bhedniya* in nature. *Trivrutta Churna* 3 gm with *Godugdha* act as *Mrudu Virechak*. It reduces *Shotha* and *Daha* of *Visarpa*.

CONCLUSION

The signs and symptoms of *Herpes zoster* and *Visarpa* are very closely resemble and the correlation can be drawn between them.

Visarpa is a disease characterised with acute manifestation of symptoms that can be easily

manageable by using *Ayurvedic* treatment protocol.

Above drugs are easily available and effective in reducing the symptoms and curing disease by their medicinal properties.

Application of *Suvarna Gairik* and *Goghurut Lepa* cooling and calming effect which reduces burning pain and sensation.

Raktmokshan (Siravedha) is best *Panchakarma* procedure for elimination of *Dushit Raktdhatu* in the body.

Thu *Kamdudha Ras*, *Chandrakala Ras*, *Paripathadi Kwath*, *Trivrutta Churna*, *Suvarna Gairik Churna* and *Goghurut Lepa* along with *Raktmokshan* can be used in the management of *Visarpa*.

Pathyapathya

Pathya: *Dadim Swaras*, *Aamalaki Swaras*, *Parushak*, *Manuka*, *Kharjur Tarpan*, *Laghu Aahar*, *Shali Tandul*, *Godhum (wheat)*, *Mudga Yush*, *Masur Yush*, *Padval* included in the diet of the patient.

Apathya: *Vidahi*, *Viruddhanna*, *Deeswap*, *Krodha*, *Ativyayam*, *Aatapsevan*, *Vanhisevan*, *Pravat* were advised to avoid.

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